

The Influence of Borrowings on the Vocabulary of the Language

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Abstract:

This article devoted to the study of the influence of borrowings on the vocabulary of the language. In Early Modern English the largest expansion of vocabulary was through word-formation processes and borrowing: mainly from Latin (perfect, logic) and French (elegant, decision), but also from other languages, such as Greek (theology, trilogy), Italian (opera, balcony), Spanish and Portuguese (alcohol, alligator).

Key words: influence, borrowings, vocabulary, Early Modern English, enlargement, word-formation, perfect, logic, elegant, decision, theology, trilogy, opera, balcony, alcohol, alligator.

The number of borrowings on Old English was insufficient. In the Middle English period there was an influx of loans. It is often opposed, that since the Norman conquest borrowing has been the chief factor in the enrichment of the English vocabulary and as a result there was a sharp decline in the productivity and role of word-formation.

Historical evidence, however, testifies to the fact that throughout its entire history, even in the periods of the mightiest influxes of borrowings, other processes no less intense, were in operation - word - formation and semantic development, which involved both native and borrowed elements. If the estimation of the role of borrowings is based on the study of words recorded in the dictionary, it is easy to overestimate the effect of the foreign words, as the number of native words is extremely small compared with the number of borrowings recorded.

The only true way to estimate the relation of the native to the borrowed element is to consider the two as actually used in speech. If one counts every word used, including repetitions, in some reading matter, the proportion of native to borrowed words will be quite different.

On such a count, every writer uses considerable more native words than borrowings. Shakespeare, for example has 90%, Milton 81%, Tennyson 88%. This shows how important is the comparatively small nucleus of native words.

Different borrowings are marked by different frequency value. Those well established in the vocabulary may be as frequent in speech as native words, whereas others occur very rarely.

The great number of borrowings in English left some imprint upon the language. The first effect of foreign influence is observed in the volume of its vocabulary. Due to its history the English language, more than any other modern language, has absorbed foreign elements in its vocabulary. But the adoption of foreign words must not be understood as were quantities change. Any importation into the lexical system brings about semantic and stylistic changes in the words of this language and changes in its synonymic groups.

It has been mentioned that when borrowed words were identical in meaning with those already in English the adopted word very often displaced the native word. In most cases, however, the borrowed words and synonymous native words (or words borrowed earlier) remained in the language, becoming more or less differentiated in meaning and use. As a result the number of synonymic groups in English greatly increased. The synonymic groups became voluminous and acquired many words rarely used. This brought about a rise in the percentage of stylistic synonyms.

As a result of the differentiation in meaning between synonymous words many native words or words borrowed earlier narrowed their meaning or sphere of application.

Abundant borrowing intensified the difference between the word stock of the literary national language and dialects as well as between British English and American English. On the one hand a number of words were borrowed into the literary national language which are not to be found in the dialects. In a number of cases the dialects have preserved some Anglo-Saxon words which were replaced by borrowings in the literary language. On the other hand, a number of words were borrowed into dialects are not used throughout the country.

In spite of the numerous outside linguistic influences and the etymological heterogeneity of its vocabulary the English language is still, in essential characteristics a Germanic language. It has retained a ground work of Germanic words and grammar. A comparative study of the nature and role of native and borrowed words show that borrowing has never been the chief means of replenishing the English vocabulary.

Word-formation and semantic development were throughout the entire history of the English language much more productive than borrowing. Besides most native words are marked by a higher frequency value.

The great number of borrowings bringing with them new phonon-morphological types, new phonetic morphological and semantic features left its imprint upon the English language. On the other hand under the influence of the borrowed element words already existing in the English changed to some extent their semantic structure, collectability, frequency and word forming ability.

Borrowing also considerably enlarged the English vocabulary and brought about some changes in English synonymic groups, in the distribution of the English vocabulary through sphere of application and in the lexical divergence between the two variants of the literary national language and its dialects.

Uzbek language is also under constant influence of borrowings. We are living in the age of progress and technology. New discoveries new inventions, bring about new notions which are accepted by languages, and Uzbek language is also among them.

The words connected with development of technology, sport terms, everyday words have been penetrating into Uzbek language from other languages, especially from English, Russian and through Russian or English from many European languages.

In its turn many Uzbek words entered the word stock of world languages, such as of sport terms: Kurash, halol, chala, the names of quinine: plov, manti, somsa, the names of clothes: chapan, yaktak, nimcha and etc.

When in two languages we find no trace of the exchange of loan words one way or the other. We are safe to infer that the two nations have had nothing to do with each other, but if they have been in contact, the number of the loan-words, and still more the quality of the loan-words, if rightly interpreted, will inform us of their reciprocal relations, they will show us which of them has been the more fertile in ideas and on what domains of human activity each has been superior of the other. If all other sources of information were closed to us except such loan-words in our modern North-European languages as «piano», «soprano», «opera», «libretto», «tempo», «adagio» etc. we should still have no hesitation in drawing the conclusion that Italian music has played a great role all over Europe.

There are many words, one a native word, the other a Romance loan, originally of either identical or similar meaning with some distinction made today, such as «freedom», and «liberty», «happiness», and «felicity», «help», and «aid», «love», and «charity», and we should find that the native word has a more emotional sense is homely and unassuming whereas the loan word is colder, aloof more dignified more formal.

Following the order of most-to-least contributing languages:

Latin: agriculture, language, justice, science, forum, circus, opium, dominatrix, religion, apostle, city, master, paper;

French: art, dance, jewel, painting, ballet, government, salon, brigade, infantry, grenade, quiche, beef, salmon;

Greek : phobia, academy, siren, lexicon, muse, odyssey, democracy, psyche, atlas, platonic, biology, comedy, tragedy, history, data;

German: blitz, strudel, kindergarten, flak, schadenfreude, schnitzel, zeitgeist, poodle, noodle, pretzel, sauerkraut, lager, zeppelin, delicatessen;

Italian: opera, soprano, piano, broccoli, fresco, spaghetti, prima donna, parmesan, pesto, viola, pizza, cappuccino, latte;

Spanish: canyon, tornado, tortilla, barricade, guitar, alligator, burrito, coyote, junta;

Dutch: buoy, cruise, dock, avast, freight, dyke, yacht, easel, landscape, sketch, booze, coleslaw, cookie, gin;

Scandinavian: smorgasbord, ski, fjord, saga, sauna, maelstrom, slalom

Japanese: karaoke, samurai, kimono, sushi, tsunami, kamikaze, geisha, judo, jujitsu, soy;

Arabic: alcohol, bedouin, harem, lute, algebra, zero, zenith, giraffe, gazelle, sultan, caravan, mosque;

Portuguese: albino, dodo, emu, fetish, tempura;

Sanskrit: avatar, karma, mahatma, swastika, yoga;

Russian: borscht, czar/tsar, icon, vodka, glasnost (a term from the Soviet Union for “open government”);

Maori kiwi: mana, moa, waka (common Maori words used in New Zealand English);
Hindi: bandanna, bangle, bungalow, juggernaut, jungle, loot, pajamas, punch (drink), shampoo;
Hebrew: sapphire, babble, brouhaha, maven, abacus, behemoth, cherub, jubilee, sabbatical, sabbath, amen;
Persian: chess, checkmate, check;
Malay: ketchup, amok;
Urdu: chintz, bungalow, cheroot, cot, many overlaps with Hindi;
Irish: boycott, brogues, clock, dig (slang), hooligan;
Afrikaans: apartheid, commando, trek, aardvark, meerkat, wildebeest;
Yiddish: Chanukkah (Hanukkah), chutzpah, kosher, lox, pastrami, schlep, klutz, oy vey, schmuck;
Chinese: dim sum, chow mein, tea, kowtow, tai chi, kung fu;
Turkish: baklava, coffee, kiosk, ottoman;
Norwegian: berserk, gun, ransack, slaughter, hell, husband, skill, bug, reindeer, dirt;
African origins: banana, bongo, banjo, cola, jazz, chimpanzee, goober, gumbo, impala, jumbo, mamba, zebra, zombie.

Sometimes, however, a language does not possess all the words necessary for it to capture all its experiences. At such times, it has to borrow words and expressions from other languages that come in contact with it. Such borrowed items help in enriching, expanding and developing the language.

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